

**CHARISMA OF A COMMUNITY AS A RESULT OF THE VALUES UNITY OF ITS PARTICIPANTS:
A SOCIO-META-ANTHROPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS****Krylova V. (Svitla V.)***candidate of philosophical sciences, doctoral student
Ukrainian State University named after Mykhailo Drahomanov***Abstract**

The methodological positions of social metaanthropology, were used in the article, in order to understand the phenomenon of charisma of a community and the crucial existential factors that determine its formation in society.

The key point was that a charismatic community, where people come together through common activities to explore and express their uniqueness, can bring out the individual charisma of its members. It was noted that the actualisation capabilities of a community can be determined by analysing the communication systems “leader-follower”, “follower-follower” and “community – others”.

Keywords: charisma of a community, charisma of a collective, group charisma, person, society, social metaanthropology.

Introduction

The modern world as well as production- and consumption-oriented societies increasingly dictate that people need to manifest and demonstrate their charisma, which also affects their interaction with the society and different communities, in which they live. Often, the society or collective itself can actualise the charisma of a person whose self-realisation is combined with the self-realisation of Others, on the basis of joint activities or even a mission.

It's important to highlight that in this study, the individual charisma of a person is viewed as a reflection of their personality and its existential charm, which expresses its spiritual, mental, and bodily integrity, as well as worldview values. Based on the above, it should be assumed that a community of charismatics, uniting to carry out a common mission, the service of which realises their existential charm, can form *group charisma*. Therefore, the charisma of a community in general and the charisma of a professional collective in particular is a unique manifestation and existential charm of this community or collective, which arises based on the unification of charismatic personalities and the worldview values they profess.

In today's world, dominated by market relations, the cult of success, wealth, and eternal youth, the charisma of communities, as well as the individual charisma of a person, is becoming increasingly manipulative. Major corporations, political organisations, and the media influence mass consciousness, vying for dominance in the global commercial arena. They employ increasingly sophisticated technologies of charisma and charismatic communication, ranging from nuanced to blunt tactics.

However, it is worth noting that the will to power and fame in any community does not lead to sincere, long-term unity and respect, even if such a community appears charismatic. This is because, in such communities, charisma is mostly used by their members as an instrument of manipulation and self-assertion, which creates only the appearance of value unity, often covering up intense competition and struggle for power and fame. Today, charismatic communities and professional collectives whose main goal is to gain power over large masses of people,

territories, corporations, etc. are mostly successful and popular. As a result, various contradictions and even hostilities arise in a number of countries, in the course of which destructive charismatics and destructive charismatic communities emerge, causing significant social challenges and, in extreme cases, leading to the decline of society.

In the context of the above trends, it is necessary to understand the charisma of a community as one that does not divide but unites people based on their values and the best manifestations of charisma. Only in this case, such a unification of charismatics exalts rather than humiliates human personality and dignity, and results in qualitative transformations of society and its inevitable evolution. Therefore, the purpose of this article was to study the phenomenon of the charisma of a community as a result of value unity, fruitful cooperation, and mutual actualisation of its members. To achieve this goal, the following tasks might be addressed: a systematic comprehension of the phenomenon of community charisma, the analysis of existential manifestations of community charisma, particularly, the professional collective in the being of society, the analysis of constructive and destructive aspects of community charisma and the outlining of the criteria of its validity.

The phenomenon of human charisma is comprehensively studied by researchers such as M. Weber, E. Trolhc, D. Emmett, R. Zohm, and others. The aspects of political leadership and charisma are analysed by K. Friedrich, A. Schweitzer, A. Wilner, J. Blondel, and others. The specifics of charismatic leadership and forms of its expression in social organisations are studied in the works of B. Bass, B. Avolio, J. Conger, R. Kanungo, and others.

The phenomenon of human pseudo-charisma and its social manifestations are analysed by J. Bensman and M. Givant, the phenomenon of fabricated charisma is studied by R. Glassman, and synthetic charisma is studied by R. Ling.

Charisma as a set of behavioural tools that leads to charismatic communication, as well as the aspects of successful charismatic leadership are analysed by J.

Antonakis, R. Dalio, W. van Edwards, Nikolaus B. Enkelman, O. F. Cabane, P. King, J. N. Landrum, J. S. Nye, J. Menge, R. Riggio, C. Hoopert.

The constructive and destructive manifestations of human nature in society and the ethical principles of the individual are evaluated by C. Helvetius, T. Hobbes, J. Locke, E. Kant, J.-J. Rousseau, S. Freud, E. Fromm, and others.

The sociological aspects of deviant human behaviour that diverge from the established values and general norms of society are analysed by E. Durkheim, T. Parsons, R. Dubin, E. Becker, E. Lemmert, F. Tannenbaum, and others.

Society as a system of associations of individuals in certain relationships and their life world is studied in the works of P. Bourdieu, E. Durkheim, K. Marx, J. Habermas, and others. The manifestations of mass society, the phenomena of masses and crowds are studied by N. Berdyaev, G. Le Bon, S. Moscovici, J. Ortega y Gasset, S. Freud, E. Fromm, O. Spengler, and others. The realities of the consumer society and manifestations of the market orientation of a person and society are comprehended in the works of such thinkers as F. Engels, J. Baudrillard, G. Debord, K. Marx, E. Fromm, and others.

Methodologically valuable for the current study is S. Krylova's approach in social metaanthropology. In this framework, S. Krylova delves into the fundamental existential dimensions of society's transcendence across its everyday, boundary, and meta-boundary states. J. Heisinga's approach to man as a playing creature, who in the act of play goes beyond the limits of everyday life, experiencing pleasure and freedom, as well as M. Buber's idea of "I-Thou" communication, in which there is an interaction of equivalent individuals who see and accept each other's deep personal manifestations, are also fruitful.

Understanding the specifics of the formation of community charisma

Every society is developed by its charismatic leaders, who form charismatic communities and professional collectives, and glorifies those who offer attractive worldview ideals that become the life trends of people. On the other hand, charismatic leaders are formed within a particular society and its culture. Therefore, in the context of analysing the formation of both individual charisma and the group charisma of a community, their mutual influence is evident. An individual's charisma is shaped by its worldview and the dynamics of personal development. It is undeniable that the society in which a charismatic individual resides can influence the formation and expression of their charisma to a certain extent. The time period, social, cultural, and other canons determine the development of a charismatic personality and the experience of charisma in the context of interaction with society.

To grasp the intricacies of group charisma formation or the charisma of a community as an existential allure emerging through the expression of individual charisma within societal relations, especially within the collective interaction context, S. Krylova's framework of social metaanthropology was adopted.

Developing the approach of metaanthropology, which comprehends the conditions of the personal transcendence of a person [12, p. 171-176], social metaanthropology focuses on the fundamental existential aspects of the transcendence of society. This approach "systematically explores the archetypal grounds for society's transcendence of the ordinary into the boundary and metaboundary ontological states" [10, p. 26]. The author notes that, in its ordinary being, society is based on the will to self-preservation and procreation, and therefore "develops mainly in a pan demographic direction; members of such a society do not live, but survive, due to the low economic level, or, conversely, refuse to have children for the sake of economic prosperity and well-being" [10, p. 26].

Society in its ultimate being, according to S. Krylova, is driven by the will to power, demonstrates deeper and more ambiguous processes, "striving for domination over the whole world" [10, p. 26], and, at the same time, strives "for knowledge and creativity, for the development of spirituality and culture" [10, p. 26]. According to the author, it is precisely this kind of society that nurtures geniuses capable of representing it on the world stage [10, p. 27]. Analysing the existential state of society in its meta-border being and outlining the prospects for the development of such a society, the researcher emphasises its fundamental manifestations: "the access to tolerance, social responsibility, and social partnership, which are ... real manifestations of beauty in its social dimensions" [10, p. 27]. It is worth clarifying that beauty in the being of society is comprehensively studied by S. Krylova through the analysis of such categories as the beauty of actions and relationships based on the beauty of a person's worldview [10, p. 169].

What are the existential factors of the formation of the charisma of a community? To begin with, it is worth defining the phenomenon of a community. In this study, a community was defined as a circle of people united by common motives for development, recreation, or any activity under the leadership of a leader. It can be a family or a team of individuals (a business team, an educational section, a scientific school, etc.) that unites people with a certain idea, activity, or mission. The diverse nature of a community (political, academic, economic, creative, community of interests, etc.) allows us to talk about the difference in social conditions in which group charisma is realized. A truly charismatic community becomes a space of mutual experience of value unity in the process of carrying out a common activity or mission, which realises the unique abilities of its members and can bring significant constructive results in society.

Furthermore, it is worth emphasising that a community becomes charismatic if it has a charismatic leader who, by actualising the charisma of followers, creates opportunities for the development of the group charisma. A leader actualises the charisma of such community through exemplifying their own personality and by establishing a dialogue space for interaction grounded in communication and co-creation. By experiencing co-creation as the highest manifestation of charismatic interaction, which takes place with the aim

of achieving a common mission, a community of individuals can create and express group charisma.

In general, the existential factors of the formation of the charisma of a community are necessarily related to the purpose of its being and activity and are also conditioned by the volitional and, as noted above, ideological impulses that guide the leader and his followers. Such impulses lead to the formation of the philosophy of a community as a common philosophy of all its members. The values, goals, and mission of the team that unites charismatic people on the path of their active, creative association coincide with their individual values, goals, and mission and determine the philosophy of the community and particularly the professional team.

In analysing the nuances of group charisma, it is crucial to investigate whether the philosophical orientation of a charismatic leader and the community, particularly the team they lead, consistently promote constructive and humane activities. After all, there are examples of inhumane results of cooperation between egoistic charismatics that lead to humiliation, suppression of human dignity, mass murder, destruction of nature, etc. In this context, it is about the constructive and destructive charisma of a community, the criteria of which are conditionally *sincere vitality*, *biophilia* (Fromm), which is realised through the co-creative implementation of the mission, or *playful vitality*, which is realised in the process of manipulative egocentric self-expression. Both the first and the second have a unifying character, but they significantly differ in their value basis and therefore in the motives that guide charismatic communities. The sincere vitality of charisma is expressed in the dynamism of progress, both personal and social. The game-like vitality of charisma is expressed in strictly controlled self-expression in order to obtain a certain result, which demonstrates the static nature of the personality and the community.

J. Huizinga emphasises the connection of playful activity with the inner world of a person in society [8, p. 105]. The author suggests the rationality of pure professionalism, which precludes any sense of playfulness in individuals and, consequently, stifles their vitality. "The behaviour of a professional is no longer playful behaviour, spontaneity... is no longer present" [8, p. 197]. Developing the author's idea, it is worth noting that by expressing the playful vitality of charisma or playing with their own charisma, a person or a team only pretends to love life, other people, and their own activities and pretend to be charismatic. In reality, they are only covering up the routine of their own life and the pattern of communication. A sincere charismatic may show some playfulness with charisma, but such playfulness, such as "escaping from ordinary reality" [8, p. 13], will not be play as pretending to be something other than oneself. Rather, such a manifestation of charisma in a community will be expressed through spontaneous self-expression, a kind of flirting with others or oneself, constructive self-reflection, and self-development, which increasingly reveals one's personality and leads to a new quality of collective results. Playing with one's own charisma, such as struggle,

competition, initiating intrigues, deliberate clashes between people, subjugating each other to one's own will, the insincere pretence of a fictional image of oneself, etc., will not allow the real charisma of a person and the charisma of a team to develop and be fully realised. In this case, the game is used by charismatics "to conceal the intentions of the social... character. In this case, it is...a pretend game" [8, p. 205].

Developing on the above, it should be noted that the actualisation capabilities of a charismatic community can be determined not only through the analysis of the "leader-follower" communication system but also the "follower-follower" and "community – others" systems, which reveal the value aspect of charisma in a variety of ways. It should be clarified that the charisma of a leader stimulates the charisma of followers when the leader's depth and integrity of personality are combined with the capability to effectively convey these qualities and their successful experiences in a specific domain through charismatic communication or collaborative creation. At the same time, communication becomes truly charismatic only when it takes place at the level of a dialogue between the charismatic I and Thou, who see each other's existential charm and focus on it. It is under these conditions, according to M. Buber, that equivalent relations between people are possible, in which "You can be comprehended as something that stands before me, perceived in its exclusivity" [2, p. 27].

Group charisma in the ordinary, boundary, and meta-boundary existential dimensions of society

When analysing the charisma of a community, it is worth focusing on the charismatic team, which implies the dynamism of interaction between participants through their active involvement in collective goals of a specific organization in which they collaborate, as well as their personal growth through gaining extensive existential experience.

Applying the methodological approach of social metaanthropology, let us hypothesise that within ordinary society, evolving amidst a pan demographic direction, there is a *practicality of the charisma* of a community and collective, which is mainly aimed to obtain material benefits or family, professional, social status. The charismatic leader inspires colleagues with his material possessions, financial wealth, and happy family, orienting followers to humbly perform routine work or study in order to obtain such benefits. He expresses his charisma in the achievement of a certain financial level and directs the actualisation and realisation of his followers' charisma in the appropriate direction.

Consequently, the leaders of these professional collectives mostly appeal to the material values of their members, encouraging them to fulfil their material dreams, acquire the things they want and enjoy them. Hence, the charisma of the community is expressed through the things they own and the ability to experience the delight of such possession. Charisma is essentially "residing" in the things and, in fact, the bodies of the members of a community, which serve as a measure and indicator of financial wealth and sometimes even

luxury. However, charismatics in such a collective often sacrifice their own inner freedom for the sake of practicality and comfort, which they strive for. On the other hand, the group charisma of such a team is also expressed through the sincerity, emotionality, and friendliness that its members show to each other. This mitigates the potential sense of loneliness that individuals may experience amidst material possessions and their pursuit. In general, the group charisma in society of ordinary being corresponds to socially recognised standards of success, namely financial security, personal and professional fulfilment. The sincerity of the vital charisma of this community is revealed in the understanding of life as a space and opportunity for a comfortable existence, and the collective's charismatic intentions in ordinariness are directed towards achieving this goal.

It is worth emphasising the interconnection of a person's individual charisma with the general charisma of a community. In a team with an ordinary worldview, the expression and feeling of a person's own charisma as exclusivity becomes complete within the framework of self-identification with a charismatic community.

The members of such a practical charismatic team are most visible in their unity, led by a leader, but they remain charismatic performers who are inscribed in the context of the group charisma. They may display individual charisma, but they can be interchangeable, for example, working in shifts.

Practical charismatic collectives and communities value aesthetics and external beauty and surround themselves with it; their members can help each other maintaining these values and inspiring each other with their own lifestyle and appearance. Based on the fact that a charismatic professional collective experiences individual and communal exclusivity and significance in terms of satisfying their own material and bodily needs, it can be said that each member transmits this life direction to each other and to society. The charisma of such communities is imbued with the will to status in its external manifestations, so people can visit expensive establishments or make expensive purchases, fueling their own existential charm with their presence.

A charismatic team led by a charismatic leader is a space that gives a person the opportunity not only to self-realise financially and allow themselves to live comfortably and with pleasure but also to spread similar life values in society through their work. However, often the real satisfaction and euphoria of freedom experienced by members of a practical charismatic professional team is felt after the end of the working day because the work takes up most of their time. In this context, it is worth emphasising the instrumental, functional nature of such a team's activities as a means of expressing the external charisma of its members, rather than their end in itself.

For example, it can be a team of beautiful young female models selected by the management, who reproduce group charisma through their bodily magnetism, energy, and cheerfulness. Such a concentration of external charisma will not go unnoticed by others, and therefore often acts as a kind of bait for customers in the retail sector. An indicator of the charismatic nature

of ordinary community is its mass appeal, such as its general acceptance and accessibility.

Such charismatic communities can inspire and engage only an audience of followers that shares their values, while others can only interact with them in a fragmented way. Being a prominent part of society and professing a culture of consumption for its own sake, material or spiritual, is the main goal of a charismatic community in its ordinary manifestations. However, the members of such communities do not achieve personal charismatic unity; they may remain friendly on the outside, but deeply spiritually alienated from each other. Moreover, having realised their own charisma through the possession of things and achieving conformity with generally accepted standards of external beauty and success, charismatic communities in ordinary being can be morally devastated by the race to impress in society, on the one hand, and to gain personal impressions, on the other.

A community and, particularly, the professional collective of society in its boundary being, driven by the will to power, expresses charisma through *ambition*. The leader of such a community challenges himself and his followers, encouraging them to personal manifestation and realisation. They demonstrate a high intellectual capacity, positioning themselves above their followers, thereby fostering in them a desire to aspire to them as a "star" and follow their lead.

In order to be in such a charismatic community, its members need to constantly go beyond their boundaries, come up with original ideas, and be in what is known as a business and creative tone. They can manipulate themselves to stay in this tone and meet a certain level of charisma, to control themselves and the situation. On the one hand, charismatics in an ambitious team are forced to constantly prove their exclusivity without feeling genuine love for themselves. On the other hand, they can imitate charisma by demonstrating playful vitality, suppressing their own uniqueness. They pursue external recognition, anticipate it from others, and strive to achieve new heights in their careers. However, they often remain in a state of internal dissatisfaction, insufficiency, and loneliness. By playing with fake charisma, members of an ambitious community escape from sincere interaction with each other and the leader. The leader himself may not notice the charisma of his followers or use it to assert himself. Such a leader "does not see the people with whom he deals as carriers of the Thou..., but regards them as centres of productive power and aspiration through which these people with their inherent abilities must be taken into account and used accordingly" [2, p. 47]. A similar manipulation of the community of a team by the leader with practical charisma is possible in the society of ordinary being.

The professional collective in a society of boundary being can be characterised by high competition due to power tendencies and the will to the glory that unfold in the process of achieving individual and common ambitious goals. In their destructive manifestations, charismatics can even commit "ugly acts" [10, p. 193], generating ugly relationships [10, p. 361], setting each other up, manipulating and ridiculing

each other for the purpose of self-assertion or career advancement. Therefore, a community in a society of boundary being may show extraordinary existential charm in public but have significant conflicts between its members inside. Such communities may pretend to recognise humanistic values, but in reality, commit crimes against society and other people. Thus, there may be a value distortion of the charisma of a community, which, on the one hand, is expressed in the interaction of participants based on ambitious goals, and on the other hand, in a competitive environment that may appear as ongoing mutual growth externally, yet existentially reveals itself through internal fragmentation and competition among charismatic individuals.

The charisma of a community in boundary being of society may be characterised by authoritarianism due to the egocentricity of its members. Such communities of charismatics can suppress their competitors using various manipulation techniques. It is about business enterprises, corporations, or research teams whose charismatic members pursue their ambitions to achieve personal recognition, social success, and fame. The members of such a community are acutely aware of their own uniqueness, and this unites them as strongly as their common goal. Nevertheless, there might also be fragmentation stemming from potential conflicts between the charismatic's personal goals and values and the collective objectives of the community they belong to. Beyond a certain threshold, such a charismatic personality may no longer conform to the community's norms of interaction and communication, and may even reject collaborative efforts, transforming into an enigmatic loner or rebel, potentially leading to their expulsion from the charismatic community.

Thus, while in the society of ordinary being, the community expresses the group charisma of practicality through the possession of things, soulfulness and emotionality, in the society of boundary being an ambitious community of charismatics is able to exercise power over people by massively manipulating their consciousness. It can be stated that such a charismatic community is a space of constant personal development, self-improvement, self-expression, and self-affirmation of both its members and others, who are inspired by its intellectual and creative dynamism, personal manifestation, and creation of things around them. However, the manifestations of the charismatic community leader's authoritarianism and egocentrism of its members can lead to separation from other communities in the competitive struggle or to their alienation from society, the so-called outsiderism.

In general, these charismatic communities have such a powerful charismatic, intellectual and passionate potential that they are able to initiate social, political, and cultural revolutions, leading society to growth or, conversely, to decline. However, egocentric ambition prevents the group charisma of communities always being open to constructive interaction with other communities and society, and as a result, it can separate itself from society by emphasising the elitism of its activities, creating closed clubs where members interact with like-minded people.

The charisma of a community in the space of society in its meta-boundary being, guided by the will to tolerate and implementing social partnership, expresses *inspiration*, which is manifested in sincere vitality and love for life in general. The leader's authentic charisma in such a community is enhanced by qualities of humaneness and compassion. They demonstrate their charisma by fostering the richness of their personal life, development, and constructive fulfillment across various domains. The creativity of such a charismatic leader is accompanied by endless enthusiasm and exuberance, which can surprise others. Under their leadership, the community's activities reflect a deliberate constructive mission that transcends personal gain and frequently holds social or even universal significance.

Humanism is the moral maxim of the charismatic leader and his community, that motivates them to perform constructive, beautiful actions [10, p. 410-411] and create beautiful relationships [10, p. 37] with others from a state of active love for themselves and others. In such a charismatic community, the personal development of its members is a contribution to the development of society and even humanity. Such a community becomes a space of unification of individual and group values of the participants and their charismatic selves, which makes innovation and progressiveness possible, free from painful, passive, or aggressive egocentricity and fierce competition.

Charismatic communities and collectives in meta-boundary social being act as a single organism, where each part of it manifests its significance through its own unique contribution to the common cause. Exploring the criteria for the formation of a true community, M. Buber notes that it arises "due to the presence of two points: it is necessary that all be in a living mutual relation to a single living cell, and it is necessary that all be in a living mutual relation to each other" [2, p. 45].

The genuine inspiration of the leader's charisma, which he imparts to their followers, forms the foundation of the community's group charisma, imbuing their interactions with self-belief and optimal pursuit of shared missions. Leaders and their teams of followers have historically driven significant revolutions that shaped human and social consciousness across various spheres of life: physics (Tesla, Einstein, Newton, etc.), astronomy (Copernicus, Galileo, etc.), medicine (Avicenna, etc.), psychoanalysis (Freud, Jung, Fromm, etc.), philosophy (Confucius, Plato, Aristotle, etc.), etc. It is thanks to their inspirational and sincere charisma that leaders formed such teams around them that helped them make the most amazing discoveries in the history of mankind, which have guided the development of human life to this day. This determines the immortality, the eternity of the charisma of such leaders and communities, and at the same time its constant relevance, which is evident through the ages.

Thus, the charisma of a community in a society of meta-boundary being is truly unifying. This group existential charm fills the members of community and humanity in general with faith in their own capabilities and inspires charismatics to make new constructive discoveries.

Conclusions

It was realised that the group charisma is an existential charm of a community that expresses the individual charisma of its members in the context of the commonality of their values, activities, and actualising relationships with each other and society.

It was noted that the constructive charisma of a community is expressed as a *sincere vitality*, which is realised by its members through the co-creative implementation of a common mission. The destructive charisma of a community is based on *playful vitality* and is realised in the process of manipulative egocentric self-expression of its leader and members. Both the former and the latter are unifying, but they significantly differ in their value basis and, therefore, in the motives that guide charismatic social communities and their leaders.

It was proved that in the society of ordinary being, the charisma of a community is *practical*, as it is mainly aimed at obtaining material wealth, professional or family status. While the professional team is noticeably friendly, its members cannot achieve deep charismatic unity, because of their personal lack of manifestation, they remain personally alienated from each other, but this alienation is replaced by spiritual and emotional unity. The charisma of such a community remains more emotionally and instinctively exciting than personally actualising.

It was noted that the charisma of a community in boundary being of society is expressed in the authoritarianism and egocentricity of its members. Such group charisma is characterised by *ambition*. The charismatic community in boundary social being is a space of constant self-establishment, self-improvement, self-expression, and self-affirmation of both its members and others, who are inspired by its intellectuality, dynamism and effectiveness, personal manifestation, and creativity. However, the authoritarianism of the leader of such a charismatic community and the egocentrism of its members can lead to separation from other communities in competition, detachment from society, the so-called outsiderism, or accentuated demonstrative elitism with emphasis on their own exclusivity.

It was realised that the charisma of a community in the space of the meta-boundary being of society with its will to tolerance and social partnership expresses *inspiration*, based on sincere vitality and love for life in general. A community with such charisma becomes a space of unification of individual and group values of the participants, as well as interaction based on the charismatic I and You, which makes innovation and progressiveness possible, freed from painful, passive, or aggressive egocentricity or fierce competition.

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